

Kinetic and Mechanistic Study of the Oxidation of Acrylic Acid by Molybdate Catalysed Hydrogen Peroxide

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Kinetic studies of the oxidation of acrylic acid by molybdate catalysed hydrogen peroxide at pH 4.0 have been carried out. The reaction is first order with respect to the substrate and catalyst, but independent of the hydrogen peroxide concentration. The rate of reaction is pH dependent. Variation of the ionic strength of the medium has no pronounced effect on the rate. Activation parameters have been evaluated and a probable mechanism of the reaction is discussed.

UNDER the catalytic action of certain transition metal derivatives hydrogen peroxide becomes a very effective epoxidising agent of olefins and ethylenic compounds¹⁻³. Kinetic studies on the molybdate catalysed epoxidation of allyl chloride⁴ and allyl bromide⁵ have been reported. In the present paper, we wish to describe the rate data, effect of pH and a probable mechanism for a better understanding of the nature of oxygen transfer process.

Experimental

The reagents used, acrylic acid, hydrogen peroxide, sodium molybdate, triethanolamine were of analytical grade. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and the desired concentration was maintained by dilution.

All kinetic runs were carried out in a thermostatic bath at the desired temperature. The reaction was started by adding the required quantity of the catalyst to a thermally equilibrated solution of the reactants. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were drawn at various time intervals and analysed for oxidant content according to the procedure already described⁶. The reaction was studied with a large excess of acrylic acid over hydrogen peroxide. By measuring the initial rate in the presence of added sodium perchlorate, it was found that the reaction rate was independent of ionic strength. Subsequently the ionic strength of the reaction mixture was not controlled.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of the reaction has been studied in aqueous solution at 40° at pH 4.0. The zero order rate plots of $[H_2O_2]$ vs time were linear for at least 80% of the reaction. This leads to a zero order kinetic dependence of rates on $[H_2O_2]$ as shown in Table 1. From the data in Table 2, it may be seen

that the rates increase linearly with increasing concentration of acrylic acid. The ratio $k_o/[acrylic\ acid]$ is practically constant in each case exhibiting the first order dependence of rate on substrate concentration. The oxidation rate, in fairly large concentration range, is linearly dependent on catalyst concentration as evident from Table 3. The plot of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[H_2O_2]$ ON REACTION RATE

$[Acrylic\ acid]=1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Na_2MoO_4]=1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp. = 40°, pH=4.0

$[H_2O_2]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_o $\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$
3.33	0.082
2.50	0.087
2.00	0.084
1.66	0.085
1.11	0.080

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING $[ACRYLIC\ ACID]$ ON REACTION RATE

$[H_2O_2]=2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Na_2MoO_4]=1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp.=4.0, pH=4.0

$[Acrylic\ acid]$ $\times 10 M$	k_o $\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_1 \times 10^4 = k_o/[acrylic\ acid]$ min^{-1}
2.00	0.207	1.03
1.00	0.101	1.01
0.50	0.055	1.10
0.33	0.041	1.24
0.24	0.026	1.04

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $[Na_2MoO_4]$ ON REACTION RATE

$[Acrylic\ acid]=1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2O_2]=2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp.=40°, pH=4.0

$[Na_2MoO_4]$ $\times 10^4 M$	k_o $\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_1 \times 10^4 = k_o/[catalyst]$ min^{-1}
3.30	0.266	0.080
2.50	0.169	0.068
2.00	0.133	0.066
1.30	0.091	0.069
1.00	0.084	0.084
0.50	0.086	0.072

$\log k_1 = k_0/[\text{acrylic acid}]$ vs $\log [\text{catalyst}]$ was linear with unit slope indicating the first order dependence on the concentration of sodium molybdate.

The pH dependence was studied at 40° in the range 3.5–7.0, the concentrations of the reactants being held constant. Triethanolamine was used to maintain the pH. A Elico digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. The rate of reaction increases linearly upto pH 5.0 as seen from the data in Table 4. At this pH, the formation of HMoO_4^- is maximum. The rates do not decrease with further increase in pH as observed in tungstate catalysed oxidation⁹. This might be due to the decomposition of peroxy molybdate ion. When the ionic strength was varied by the addition of sodium perchlorate, no change in the rate constant has been observed. This suggests that at least one uncharged species takes part in the rate determining step.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF pH ON RATE OF REACTION

[Acrylic acid] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ M, $[\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ M, Temp. = 40°

pH	$k_0 \times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹
3.50	0.025
4.00	0.084
4.50	0.133
5.00	0.166
6.00	0.320
7.00	0.400

The stoichiometry of the reactions corresponds to $\Delta[\text{acrylic acid}]/\Delta[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] \sim 1:1$. The reactions are carried out at different temperatures with a view to compute the Arrhenius parameters. The plot of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ is found to be linear. The values of $\Delta E^\ddagger$, $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are 65.6 ± 5 kJ mol⁻¹, 76.8 ± 3 kJ mol⁻¹ and -112.5 ± 8 JK mol⁻¹ respectively.

Mechanism: Although molybdate exists as MoO_4^{2-} in alkaline solution, it undergoes hydrolysis as the pH is lowered. In aqueous solution HMoO_4^- is believed to be formed by the hydrolysis of MoO_4^{2-} at pH 4.0,

It forms, with hydrogen peroxide, peroxy acid anions according to the reaction⁹,

This shows that significant proportions of molybdate in our solution will be present as peroxy complexes.

The data reported here indicate the successive coordination of the oxidant and the substrate to the catalyst, followed by a redox process in the complex, *i.e.*

where, P is the final product. If the processes (4) and (5) are fast compared with (6), the overall rate expressed as the formation rate of the final reaction product P, is

$$-\frac{d[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]}{dt} = k_5 [\text{Intermediate complex}] \quad (7)$$

The dependence of the reaction rate on pH and the reagent concentration can be derived by the steady state method. Assuming the steady state condition for the intermediate, we get,

$$\text{[Intermediate complex]} = \frac{k_3}{k_4 + k_5} [\text{HMoO}_5^-] [\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOOH}] \quad (8)$$

The total $[\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4]$ added as catalyst is present in the form,

$$[\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4]_{\text{total}} = [\text{MoO}_4^{2-}] + [\text{HMoO}_4^-] + [\text{Intermediate complex}] \quad (9)$$

From the equilibrium,

$[\text{HMoO}_4^-]$ can be evaluated from equations (9) (after neglecting the last term) and (10),

$$[\text{HMoO}_4^-] = \frac{K[\text{H}^+][\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4]_{\text{total}}}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \quad (11)$$

Assuming that HMoO_4^- reacts with H_2O_2 instantaneously and completely, $[\text{HMoO}_4^-]$ can be substituted for $[\text{HMoO}_5^-]$ in equation (8). Thus,

$$\text{[Intermediate complex]} = \frac{k_3 K [\text{H}^+] [\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4]_{\text{total}} [\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOOH}]}{k_4 + k_5 (1 + K[\text{H}^+])} \quad (12)$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]}{dt} = \frac{k' K [\text{H}^+] [\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4]_{\text{total}} [\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOOH}]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \quad (13)$$

where, $k' = k_3 k_5 / (k_4 + k_5)$. Equation (13) is in good agreement with the experimental data. This also accounts for the pH dependence.

It is noteworthy that $\Delta S^\ddagger$ value for the reaction under study is negative. A highly oriented transition state can however be inferred on the basis of the large negative entropy of activation.

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References

1. G. G. ALLAN, U. S. Pat. 3 156 709/1964.
2. M. MUGDAN and D. P. YOUNG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2988.
3. G. G. ALLAN and A. N. NROGI, *J. Catal.*, 1970, **19**, 256.
4. P. KHARE and G. L. AGRAWAL, *J. Inst. Chem., Calcutta*, 1983, **55**, 137.
5. I. AHMAD and C. M. ASHRAF *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **17**, 302.
6. G. L. AGRAWAL and A. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1032.
7. P. KHARE and G. L. AGRAWAL, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1983, **23**, 207.
8. N. V. SIDGWICK, "The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Oxford, 1950, Vol II, p. 1045.